

IR1545, DV85, and RP291-20 were consistently resistant or susceptible to bacterial blight, while IR20 and Cempo

Selak varied in reaction. There was no longer any significant interaction with leaf positions within each group. Larger

differences in leaf position were detected among varieties of the latter than among those of the former group. *W*

Pest management and control

DISEASES

Transmission of rice ragged stunt disease by *Nilaparvata lugens* in Japan

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The transmission of rice ragged stunt disease by the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* that had been reared on rice plants in Sapporo, Japan, for 4 years was studied. After 1-day acquisition feeding on diseased plants of the line IR3839-1, infected in the Philippines, 50 brown planthoppers (BPH) were tested for infectivity by daily serial transmission to 1,270 seedlings of the variety Mihonishiki for 40 consecutive days (except when insects died earlier). The experiment was carried out in a temperature-controlled greenhouse (25–28°C) at the University of Hokkaido, Japan.

Twenty-eight percent of the tested BPH were active transmitters. Both female and male adults and both brachypterous and macropterous forms were able to transmit the disease. The latent period ranged from 5 to 11 days after acquisition feeding, averaging 8.6 days. The infective insects transmitted the disease to 1 to 31 or more seedlings during their life spans. The retention period ranged from 9 to 41 days or more, after acquisition feeding (some insects did not die on the last day of the transmission test, 41 days after acquisition feeding). The disease-transmitting days were from 33 to 100% (av. 81%) of the period from the time the insects became infective until the end of the transmission test.

The BPH in Japan did not differ strikingly from the BPH in the Philippines in either percentage of active transmitters or latent period. But they

infected more rice seedlings during their life spans, had longer retention periods, and had higher percentages of disease-transmitting days than the Philippine BPH tested at IRRI.

Further studies will be conducted to determine if the differences are due to ecotype of the insect or conditions of the transmission test. *W*

Host range of rice ragged stunt virus

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Plants of several rice species were inoculated by brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* that were viruliferous for ragged stunt disease. Most of the plants did not become infected. Among *Oryza* species, however, *O. sativa*, *O. latifolia*, and *O. nivara* were all infected. The infected plants of *O. latifolia* (Fig. 1, 2) and *O. nivara*

(Fig. 3) showed symptoms of stunting, ragged leaves, vein swellings, and nodal branches. Those symptoms are similar to the ones on infected *O. sativa*.

Brown planthoppers recovered the virus from the diseased plants of *O. latifolia* and *O. nivara* and transmitted it successfully to rice plants.

Consequently, *O. sativa* is not the only host of ragged stunt. *W*

1. An *O. latifolia* plant infected with ragged stunt.
2. Ragged leaves of a diseased *O. latifolia* plant.
3. Healthy plants of *O. nivara* (left) and plants infected with ragged stunt (right).